

A DISTINCTNESS APPROACH TO CLITIC COMBINATIONS IN ROMANCE¹

Abstract: This paper analyses the combinatorial restrictions that operate in clitic clusters in certain Eastern Iberian varieties (Aragonese, Spanish, and Catalan). In particular, I focus on the combination of third person clitics. As is well known, in some Romance varieties the combination of a third person accusative clitic and a third person dative clitic is banned (so-called **le lo* restriction, cf. Bonet 1991; Cuervo 2013; Nevins 2007; Ordóñez 2002, 2012; Perlmutter 1971). In order to license this troublesome combination, languages resort to different ‘repair strategies’ modifying the structure of one of the merged clitics. In the literature on clitic combinations, there have been two main proposals of analysis: morphological and syntactical. In this paper, I put forward an analysis based on the Distinctness Condition (cf. Hiraiwa 2010; Neeleman and Van de Koot 2005; Perlmutter 1971; Richards 2010; Van Riemsdijk 1998; Yip 1998). Specifically, I argue that the restrictions that constraint clitic combinations are due to the impossibility to linearize two identical syntactic objects, such as <XP, XP> (cf. Chomsky 2013, 2015; Moro 2000; Richards 2010). From this perspective, cross-linguistic variation is the result of different ‘repair strategies’ languages deploy to make <XP, XP> objects linearizable (cf. Richards 2010).

Key words: Clitic Clusters, Eastern Iberian, Distinctness, Accusative, Dative

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CL.LOC CL.LOC talked about football
'In the library, with Pilar, Roser talked about football.'

In addition, this approach allows us to discuss the phenomenon of “clitic clustering” along with other cases where two complements appear in the same domain (phenomena such as Differential Object Marking, cf. Alexiadou & Anagnostopoulou 2007; López 2012; Rodríguez Mondoñedo 2007; Torrego 1998). From a theoretical perspective, this approach makes it possible to make more general observations regarding the way in which syntax operates (and the constraints it is subject to), thus raising deeper theoretical questions.

The present paper is organized as follows: Section 2 focusses on the empirical properties of clitic clusters in three Eastern Iberian varieties (Aragonese, Catalan, and Spanish). Section 3 puts forward a Distinctness-based analysis of the third person clitic combinations already presented in the previous section. Also, Section 3 is further subdivided as follows: the first subsection presents the Distinctness Condition; and, in the second subsection, I explain the assumptions about the cliticization process and the clitic composition that are relevant to the analysis. Then, I focus on the parametric variation concerning accusative and dative clitics. Finally, I describe how the combinatorial restriction operates and accounts for the cross-linguistic variation. In the conclusion, I provide some finalizing remarks.

2. COMBINATORIAL RESTRICTIONS IN CLITIC CLUSTERS

This section describes the empirical properties of clitic clusters in Eastern Iberian (Spanish, Catalan, and Aragonese)². As the literature has shown, clitics can modify their morphological shape in particular contexts. This occurs when they appear isolated (such phenomena is known as *leísmo*, *loísmo*, *laísmo* cf. Bleam 1999; Fernández Ordóñez 1999; Ormazabal and Romero 2013; Romero 2008 or in ‘recycling’ contexts, cf. Longa, Lorenzo and Rigau 1996; Roca 1996) or in combination with other clitics (yielding a cluster). This section focuses on the second scenario. To be more exact, in the first subsection, I discuss combinations of third person clitics.

2.1. **Le lo* Restriction

The restriction on clusters formed by two third person clitics has been attested widely in the literature (cf. Bonet 1991; Cuervo 2013; Ordóñez 2002, 2012; Perlmutter 1971; Pescarini 2010; Nevins 2007; Walkow 2012, 2013). The result of this combination has been called ‘opaque,’ in the sense that one of the two clitics cannot maintain their original structure (cf. Bonet 1991, 2008). The following section reviews these facts in Spanish, Catalan, and Aragonese.

2.1.1. *Spanish*

². Due to space limitations, I only present data from Catalan, Spanish, and Aragonese. But the scenario is similar in other Romance Languages (cf. Manzini and Savoia 2010; Pescarini 2015, 2010 for examples in Italian varieties).

In Spanish, the combination of the third person dative clitic *le* and the accusative one *lo* is banned, as exemplified as follows in (6).

- (6) i. IO cliticization: Juan **le** compró un libro a María.
 Juan CL.DAT.3SG bought a book to María
 ‘Juan bought a book to María.’
- ii. DO cliticization: Juan **lo** compró
 Juan CL.AC.3SG bought
 ‘Juan bought it.’
- iii. *IO OD cliticization: Juan **le** **lo** compró
 Juan CL.DAT.3SG CL.AC.3SG bought
 ‘Juan bought it to him/her.’
- iv. IO OD cliticization: Juan **se** **lo** compró
 Juan SE CL.AC.3SG bought
 ‘Juan bought it to him/her.’

(Ordoñez 2002: 202)

Clitics *le* and *lo* can pronominalize the Indirect Object *a María* (cf. (6i)) and the Direct Object *un libro* (cf. (6ii.)) respectively. This cannot occur if both clitics pronominalize the two objects at once (cf. (6iii)). In this scenario, one of the two clitics manifests some changes in their morphological structure, as shown below.

Spanish resorts to the so-called ‘Spurious SE’ (cf. Bonet 1991; Cuervo 2013; Ordóñez 2002) to rescue the combination in (6ii), as exemplified in (6iv). In this case, the dative clitic *le* is replaced by the clitic *se* in some Spanish varieties³. In addition, the accusative clitic is also subject to morphological changes. As the data in (7) shows, the accusative clitic *lo* manifests the same form of the dative *le*⁴ in ‘Spurious-SE’ contexts. Moreover, this clitic matches with the dative clitic’s number exemplified in (7), (8) and (9). As shown below, *le(s)* agrees with the number of the Indirect Object.

³ This data in particular, comes from Aragonese Spanish. Specifically, the corpus COSER has collected this data in some locations of Teruel (cf. Inés Fernández Ordóñez, COSER).

⁴ Gallego and Roca (2016) offer similar data in the formation of clitic groups with impersonal ‘se’:

- (i) A Juan, [lo / *le] vieron contento. (Mexican Spanish)
 to Juan, CL.AC.3SG CL.DAT.3SG saw happy
 ‘To Juan, they saw him happy.’
- (ii) A Juan, se le vio contento. (Mexican Spanish)
 To Juan, SE CL.DAT.3SG saw happy
 ‘To Juan, he was seen happy.’
- (iii) A María, se le vio contenta. (Mexican Spanish)
 to Maria, SE CL.DAT.3SG saw happy
 ‘To María, she was seen happy.’

The interesting fact about these data is that the presence of *se* favors *leísmo*, an option that is not available in this variety of Spanish for situations without clitic groups. This possibility has been related to the fact that the *se* clitic is involved in *v* becoming ϕ defective (cf. Colomina, Gallego and Roca 2016; Raposo and Uriagereka 1996).

- (7) Algunos se quejaban que el maestro.[...], pero yo todo
 some SE complained that the teacher but I all
se le debo a él.
 SE CL.DAT.3SG owe to him

‘Some complained that the teacher, [...], but I owe everything to him.’

- (8) Lo que es nuestros hijos, pues claro,
 the that is our sons well of.course
 ya no han visto jugar y **se les** explicamos
 already no have seen play and SE CL.DAT.3SG explain

‘With regards to our sons, well, of course, they have not seen play it, and we explain it to them.’

- (9) ¡Y no me entendéis nada!, yo es que
 and no CL.DAT.1SG understand nothing I is that
 digo, yo digo, es, no hará falta
 said I said is no will.do lack
 decir **se les...**
 said SE CL.DAT.3PL

‘You do not understand me at all! I said... It will not be necessary tell it to them.’

(Alcalá de la Selva (Teruel), COSER 4102)

Furthermore, in Basque Spanish and in some varieties of American Spanish⁵ (cf. Suñer and Yépez 1988) there is a tendency to elide the Direct Object (phenomenon known as null object or object pro-drop cf. Campos 1986; Franco and Landa 1992; Landa 1995; Ortiz de Urbina 1989; Rizzi 1982)⁶. This elision is more common in ditransitive contexts, when the dative and the accusative clitics are combined. As seen in (10) and (11), when the dative and the accusative clitic are put together, the second one is elided. Interestingly, in these scenarios the dative clitic maintains its original structure with *le*. Thus, contrary to the previous data, the ‘Spurious SE’ clitic does not need to emerge.

- (10) También tengo las fotos del bote de J.
 also have the photos of.the boat of J.
 Los padres de J. quieren que **les** mandemos
 the parents of J. want that CL.DAT.3SG send

‘Also I have the photos of the J.’s boat. J.’s parents want us to send them.’

- (11) ¿Quién le contó? Dicen que **le** contó su hermana
 who CL.DAT.3SG tell said that CL.DAT.3SG tell his sister

⁵ In Yépez & Suñer (1988) data are provided from Quiteño Spanish.

⁶ Although I can not go into further details, it is worth pointing out that the literature on the topic defends a hierarchy to elide the DO (cf. Campos 1986; Franco and Landa 1991; Landa, 1995, Rizzi 1982, Ortiz de Urbina 1989). Generally, in Basque Country Spanish this elision is related to Animacy hierarchy: if DOs are [-animate] they are elided; on the contrary, [+animate] DOs are pronominalizable by dative clitic *le* (cf. Landa 1995 for some exceptions).

'Who told it to him/her? They said that his sister tell it to him/her.'

(Landa 1995: 126)

Let us consider one final phenomenon related to the 'Spurious SE'. In some American Spanish areas (such as Mexico and Venezuela), there is a linguistic phenomenon known as feature transfer (cf. Bonet 1991; Heggie and Ordóñez 2005), which occurs when the clitic *se* emerges. This phenomenon refers to a situation whereby the accusative clitic manifests a feature of the dative, usually its number. This feature cannot be expressed by the clitic *se* because it does not have number features (**ses*).

As can be observed in (13), the plural feature of the dative clitic seems to be appended to the accusative clitic, similarly to the previously mentioned cases of the Aragonese Spanish (see above in (8) and (9)).

(12) Yo doy eso a ellos
I give that to them
'I give that to them'

(13) Yo se los doy
I SE CL.AC.3PL give
'I give it to them.'

(Kayne 2000: 106)

2.1.2. Catalan

Now let us examine the same phenomenon in Catalan. In this language, there is an abundant range of solutions to replicate the combination of two third person clitics according to different Catalan varieties. For example, in Ribagorçan Catalan, the dative clitic *li* is replaced by the locative clitic *hi* and, in some areas, the accusative clitic acquires the feminine form *la* (cf. Giralt 1998; Sistac 1993), while, in others, it maintains the form *lo*.

(14) OI clitization i. **Li** he dit a la meva germana.
 CL.DAT.3SG have.said to the my sister
'I have said to my sister.'

OD clitization ii. **Lo** hi hai dit no sé quantes vegades
 CL.AC.3SG CL.LOC have.said no known how.many times
'I have said it to him I do not known hoy many times.'

*OI OD clitization iii. **Lo** **li** he dit no sé quantes vegades
 CL.AC.3SG CL.DAT.3SG have.said no known how.many times
'I have said it to him I do not known hoy many times.'

OI OD clitization iv. **Lo** **hi** he dit no sé quantes vegades
 CL.AC.3SG CL.LOC have.said no known how.many times
'I have said it to him I do not known hoy many times.'

(Giralt 1998: 86)

As exemplified in (14i) and (14ii), accusative and dative third person clitics appear to pronominalize the Direct Object and the Indirect Object when isolated. When both clitics are combined, the result is subject to changes. Specifically, the dative clitic is replaced by the locative clitic (cf. (14 iv)).

North-Western Catalan varieties stand in close contact with Aragonese. In these situations, it is common that transfer of features between the two clitics occurs. As mentioned earlier, the same happens in the case of American Spanish (cf. Bonet 1991; Heggie and Ordóñez 2005).

- (15) Los **hi** **dic** a estos críos.
CL.AC.3PL CL.LOC said to this boys
'I said it to this boys.'

(Giralt 1998: 90)

This only occurs when the clitic dative is substituted by the locative clitic. As in Spurious SE contexts, the locative clitic cannot manifest the number features of the dative (**his*). To conclude, let me now present data from other Catalan varieties. Central variants align with North-Western variants in that the dative is replaced by the locative.

- (16) **L'** **hi** diré.
CL.AC.3SG CL.LOC will.say
'I will say it to him/her.'

(Bonet 1991)

Finally, in Mallorcan Catalan the clitic that seems to elide is the accusative one (cf. (17)).

- (17) Es llibre, a nen Joan **li** don
the book to boy Joan CL.DAT.3SG give
'The book, to boy Joan, I give it.'

2.1.3. Aragonese

Before finishing this section, I consider the strategies adopted by Aragonese varieties to avoid the **le lo* combination. As exemplified in (18iii), the combination of dative and accusative clitics is also disallowed in Aragonese.

- (18) OI clitization i. **Le** compro a ell els bous.
CL.DAT.3SG buy to him the oxen
'I buy him the oxen.'
OD clitization ii. **Els** compro.
CL.AC.3SG buy
'I buy it.'
*IO OD clitization iii. Els bous **els** **le** compro a ell.

the oxen CL.AC.3PL CL.DAT.3SG buy to him
'I buy him the oxen.'

(Saura 1998: 170)

In these Central Iberian varieties, different strategies are resorted to in order to avoid this restriction (cf. Arnal 1998; Kuhn 2008; Nagore 1986). For instance, Eastern Aragonese dialects follow the same mechanism Catalan deploys. That is, the locative clitic *ie* replaces the dative clitic *le*, as exemplified in (19).

(19) Els bous **els** **ie** compro a ell.
the oxen CL.AC.3PL CL.LOC buy to him
'I buy him the oxen.'

In contrast, Southern, Western, and Central varieties use the partitive clitic *ne* to replace the accusative one, as the examples in (20) and (21) reveal.

(20) A máquina **l'** **en** dejaban en as casas.
the machine CL.AC.3SG CL.PART left in the houses
'The machine, they would leave it to him in the houses'

(21) Marta, torna **lis** **ne** en un momento
Marta, back CL.DAT.3PL CL.PART in a moment
'Marta, give it back to them immediately'

(Landa 2005: 119)

In conclusion, this subsection has shown that, in general, the varieties under discussion reject the combination of two third person clitics **le lo*. Further, it has also been shown that the combinations that appear in their place are either 'Spurious SE' or locative *hi* replacing the clitic dative, or even the partitive *en* replacing the accusative clitic. A summary of the possibilities to fix the problem that third person clitic combinations trigger is sketched in (22) and (23):

(22) MODIFY DATIVE:

- A. OPTION 1: Spurious SE, 'se lo/le/∅' combination (cf. (6) – (11) above)
- B. OPTION 2: locative, 'lo hi' combination (cf. (14), (15), (16), (19) above)

(23) MODIFY ACCUSATIVE:

- Partitive, 'l'en' combination (cf. (20), (21) above)

2.3. Interim summary

(24)

<i>Language</i>	<i>Repair strategy 3-3</i>
Spanish	Spurious SE
(Basque Country, American) Spanish	Null object
Catalan, East Aragonese	Dative>locative

As we can see in the table above (24), with regards to third person combinations, Spanish uses Spurious SE or a null object. In Catalan and East Aragonese, the dative clitic undergoes some change, especially since the locative replaces the dative. Finally, in other Aragonese varieties, the clitic that is subject to change is the accusative one, which becomes a partitive.

3. A DISTINCTNESS APPROACH

In this section, I present an analysis of the clitic combination intricacies shown in the previous section that is based on the Distinctness Condition (cf. Hiraiwa 2010; Richards 2010).

As mentioned in the introduction, I consider that addressing a topic such as the combination of clitics within this framework presents different advantages. From an empirical point of view, the distinctness condition allows the analysis of different types of combinations that at first glance might appear to be unrelated. Further, this approach connects the vastly studied topic of clitic clusters together with a wide range of phenomena that are also affected by this restriction. As shown in the subsection 3.1. below, the different phenomena present similar alternatives to avoid the violation of this restriction. From a theoretical perspective, the treatment of the clitic combinations within this framework permits questioning aspects concerning the architecture of the grammar, as it is discussed in subsection 3.2.2.

3.1. The Distinctness Condition

This subsection introduces the Distinctness Condition proposed by Richards (2010), which I refer to throughout the next sections. This condition can be described as follows:

(25) Distinctness

If a linearization statement $\langle \alpha, \alpha \rangle$ is generated, the derivation crashes at PF.

[Taken from Richards 2010: 5]

The formulation in (25) indicates that two elements that are transferred to the phonetic interface cannot be identical because they could not be linearized. This could occur, for example, in (26a), where two directly assembled DPs should be linearized. The derivation is legitimate in (26b), where the preposition *of* is inserted in order to break the symmetry in (26a)—in other words, to go from $\langle \text{DP}, \text{DP} \rangle$ to $\langle \text{DP}, \text{PP} \rangle$.

- (26) a. *The destruction the city.
 b. The destruction **of** the city.

Let us look at this in more detail. Richards (2010), following Chomsky (1995, 2000, 2001), assumes that syntax does not encode information about linear order and that the different nodes are linearized in the Transfer Domain, according to the Linear Correspondence Axiom (LCA cf. Kayne 1994). Richards (2010) also assumes that the

Transfer operation is cyclic and occurs at different moments of the derivation, namely, each time a phase is transferred (cf. Chomsky 2000, 2001). In Richards' (2010) system, CPs, vPs, DPs, and PP/KPs are phases.

In order for the derivation not to crash at PF, Richards (2010) defends that there are three strategies for two nodes to be 'distinct.' The first strategy consists in adding structure; Richards (2010) refers to the possibility that a DP can be converted into a PP or a KP by adding a preposition or a case marker (as in (26) above).

The second strategy consists in eliminating structure; In this case, one of the two functional categories could become a lexical category which, following Richards (2010), are immune to distinctivity effects. According to Richards (2010) this happens, for example, in restructuring contexts (cf. Cinque 2004; Hernanz and Rigau 1984; Wurmbrand 2004). As is known from Longobardi (1980), there exist in languages like Italian a restriction that prohibits the concatenation of two infinitives. This filter also has different exceptions. In terms of DIS, the appearance of two infinitives in the same phase involves the linearization of a structure of type $\langle v, v \rangle$. The exceptions to this filter provided by Longobardi (1980) come from contexts of restructuring, as demonstrated by the rise of the clitic in (27).

- (27) a. Giovanni comicia a volerlo fare (Italian)
 Giovanni begins to want-INF-it do-INF
 'Giovanni is beginning to want to do it.'
 b. *Giovanni comincia a voler farlo

Richards (2010) assumes Wurmbrand's (1998) analysis, according to which restructuring verbs lack the CP and vP layers, being characterized, therefore, by the VP layer. The result of the combination of two infinitives in the contexts of restructuring does not then involve the combination of two $\langle v, v \rangle$.

The third strategy is concerned with movement. Low copies are not pronounced at the phonetic interface, so they are inert for linearization processes. We can see an example of this strategy in (28). In the sentence (28a), the following non-linearizable object is generated: $\langle PP, PP \rangle$. As we can observe in (28b) and (28c), if one of these phrases is moved to the left periphery of the sentence, the object to be linearized is: $\langle PP, \overline{PP} \rangle$.

- (28) a. ??Juan le presentó a María a Pedro.
 Juan CL.DAT.3SG introduced to María to Pedro.
 'John introduced Mary to Peter.'
 b. A Pedro, Juan le presentó a María
 c. A María, Juan le presentó a Pedro.

Although I will not expand on these strategies in the present section, I will return to this topic of discussion in future sections ⁷. In the next subsections I lay out the assumptions I'll be making regarding the cliticization process and the composition of the clitics that are relevant to the analysis.

⁷ These strategies seem to violate different principles. One of them is the 'Inclusiveness Condition' (cf. Chomsky 1995) and the 'Non-tampering Condition'. The strategies Richards mentions involve the alteration of the structure already created, an operation that is strongly rejected in standard minimalist formulations (Chomsky 1995, 2000, 2001), an issue to which we will return in section 5.3.3.

3.2. The clitization process

In this subsection I elucidate the different proposals that can be found in the literature regarding the way in which the cliticization process takes place (cf. Gallego 2016; Kayne 1975, 1989, 1991; Rizzi 1986; Roberts 2010; Ordóñez 2002; Uriagereka 1995). I will then present the proposal assumed here.

From a syntactic point of view, there are two main hypotheses for analyzing cliticization: (i) the movement hypothesis (cf. Kayne 1975; 1989, 1991; Rizzi 1986; Uriagereka 1995) and (ii) the base generation hypothesis (cf. Fernández Soriano 1989; Sportiche 1998; Suñer 1988; Zubizarreta 1999). As exemplified in (27), the authors who defend the first hypothesis argue that clitics are determiners that move (head movement) and are incorporated into the verb (or some associated projection).

The positions proposed to host the clitic are diverse: Kayne (1975, 1989) argues that clitics are attached to T, whereas Uriagereka (1995) argues that they are generated within a big-DP (following big-DP hypothesis cf. Belletti 2005; Kramer 2012; Torrego 1992; Uriagereka 1995) and move to a functional category F, between TP and CP. The authors who defend the second hypothesis, depicted in (27), argue that clitics are agreement markers that are directly generated in a verbal position. According to these authors, clitics are associated to an empty category (*pro*) that is placed in a relevant (argumental) position within the VP.

In this paper, I will assume Gallego's proposal (2016), which combines aspects of Chomsky (2000, 2001), Torrego (1998, 2002), and Uriagereka (1995). The main idea of

this proposal is that clitics constitute a case of XP movement at the edge of the phase.⁸ The trigger of movement and the target position of cliticization are the result of the combination of two independent factors: on the one hand, the phonologically defective character of clitics (which need to be attached to a host) and, on the other hand, the place where the $-\phi$ features appear: v^* .

This option presents advantages over the models based on the agreement operation (cf. Gallego 2016 to see all arguments). Among others, this model can account for the semantic effects of cliticization, such as the obligatorily specific character of the accusative clitic (cf. Uriagereka 1995) or the semantic effects observed in clitic climbing (cf. Uriagereka 2002). Unlike long-distance agreement, XP movement to the edge of the phase has been associated with such semantic effects (cf. Chomsky 2001). In addition, one of the predictions of this analysis is that the cliticization process will be subject to local restrictions such as Phase Impenetrability Condition (cf. Chomsky 2000, 2001); in particular, notice that the examples in (28) and (29) show that clitic climbing is sensitive to such a condition, as clitics can only escape from ϕ -defective (phase-less) domains:

- (31) Juan (***lo**) dice que **lo** ha visto.
 Juan CL.AC.3SG say that CL.AC.3SG has.seen
 'Juan says he has seen it.'
- (32) Juan (**lo**) puede ver (**lo**)
 Juan CL.AC.3SG can see-INF CL.AC.3SG
 'Juan can see it.'
- (33) Juan (**lo**) puede ver (**lo**)
 Juan CL.AC.3SG hizo see-INF CL.AC.3SG
 'Juan made him see it.'

As can be observed in (28), clitics cannot raise from a clause with an inflected verb, but they could in contexts involving the so-called restructuring verbs (cf. Cinque 2004, 2006; Hernanz & Rigau 1984; Wurmbrand 2001, 2004), where a biclausal structure becomes a monoclausal. The relevant characteristic of these verbs is that the embedded clause features a defective functional category. That is to say, it does not possess the pertinent ϕ -features to assign a case to the pronoun and, therefore, it forces it to remain in its clause. For this reason, the clitic can raise from the non-finite subordinate clause to the finite verb (cf. (32), (33)).

Gallego (2016) focuses on the direct object's cliticization. At this point, we must consider how this process occurs in the rest of the clitics of the paradigm, specifically in the indirect object. As mentioned above, most of the authors assume a unified treatment of the cliticization process: the clitics are either generated directly in its base or in a complement position in VP and, subsequently, they cliticize. Ormazabal and Romero (2007, 2017) argue for a mixed approach to dative and accusative clitics. In particular,

⁸ There are different empirical arguments to defend the maximal projection status of clitics (cf. Donati 2006). One of them comes from the observation that clitics do not select complements, as opposed to determinants. If we adopt an analysis in which clitics are transitive determinants (cf. Abney 1986; Post 1966; Torrego 1988; Uriagereka 1995), we should assume that clitics are always associated with a "pro" in the complement position. Note that whether clitics select a "pro" or default phrasal objects, the result is the one we are defending here.

these authors defend that dative clitics and first and second person accusative clitics are agreement markers generated in a verbal position. On the contrary, accusative third person clitics result from XP movement (an incorporated determiner, in the line of what has been commented so far; cf. Uriagereka 1988).

The mixed hypothesis can be defended on empirical grounds (cf. Ormazabal and Romero 2007, 2013). The main argument comes from the phenomenon known as clitic doubling. While clitic doubling is generally possible with IO, it is rejected in European Spanish in the case of DO, as it can be observed in the contrast shown in (34) and (35)⁹.

(34) **Le** recomendé un libro a los estudiantes
 CL.DAT.3SG recommended a book to the students
 'I recommended a book to the students.'

(35) (***La**) vi la casa.
 CL.AC.3SG see the home
 'I see the home.'

Based on the literature, I make two assumptions in what follows. The first assumption is that the DO clitics are placed in the phase-edge position of v*, according to the mentioned movement process (cf. Gallego 2016). The second assumption is that the IO clitics are generated directly where we see them (cf. Ormazabal and Romero 2007) as shown in (36).

Although I assume the structure of (36), the proposal that I will present below is compatible with the other hypotheses mentioned. What is relevant for the analysis is that

⁹ This occurs with DPs. When DO is a strong pronoun, clitic doubling is mandatory in all variants, as we observe below:

(i) **La** vi a ella
 CL.AC.3SG see to she
 'I see her.'

(ii) ***Vi** a ella.
 see to she
 'I see her.'

at the moment of the derivation in which the transfer operation occurs, both clitics are within the same domain: the edge of v^* . As discussed in Section 3.2.1., distinctivity effects occur within these phasal domains. In the next section, I discuss the internal composition of clitics.

3.3. The internal structure of clitics

Another issue that has also aroused great interest in the literature (and which is very relevant for the analysis of the data) is the internal composition of the clitics and their label (cf. Cardinaletti and Starke 1999; Déchaine and Wiltschko 2002; Harley and Ritter 2002; Picallo 2007). In the following pages I present the assumptions I will base my approach to the composition of the clitics on; afterwards, I return to the combination of the clitics in more detail.

To be more precise, I first describe the internal structure of dative clitics. The main idea that I develop in the first section is that the dative is the combination of accusative and locative (cf. Martin 2012; Boeckx and Martin 2013). Then, in the following section I focus on the specific structure and label of the accusative and dative clitics. Finally, I discuss some issues related to the cross-linguistic variation that can be established between Spanish and Catalan.

3.3.1. The dative clitic: a derived clitic

For the purposes of this paper, I will build on Boeckx and Martin's (2013) analysis of dative clitics (cf. Martin 2012; Kayne 1993, 2008; Szabolcsi 1986 for more discussion). According to them, the third-person dative clitic is not a grammatical primitive in the Romance languages, but a complex unit. They phrase their main idea as follows:

(37) DATIVE = ACCUSATIVE + x , where x = DEIXIS

[Taken from Martin 2012]

The main hypothesis defended by this authors is that the dative clitic is a derived object, resulting from the combination of two primitive notions: accusativity and deixis (or locativity)¹⁰. Boeckx and Martin (2013), following Kayne's (2008) proposal, argue that the morpheme representing deixis is the locative clitic (*hi* in Catalan)¹¹. Hence, the structure of (34) corresponds to the one in (38).

¹⁰ The notion that the dative contains the accusative is not new. Although I cannot go into further details, a phenomenon that has been related to that is Differential Object Marking (cf. Aissen 2003; Leonetti 2004; Torrego 1998, 1999; among others). Marantz also presents the same idea in his theory of dependent case (cf. Marantz 1991). In the same line, the existence of a universal case hierarchy (cf. Caha 2009) aligns with this hypothesis.

¹¹ In contrast to Martin (2012) and Boeckx & Martin (2013), other authors (cf. Bonet 1991, 1995; Harris 1995; Solà-Pujols 1998) interpret the [i] of the dative clitic [li] as a dative case mark. One argument against this analysis is the fact that first and second person dative clitics do not manifest the morpheme [i]. Clitic *hi* has also been analyzed as an inanimate dative (cf. Rigau 1978, 1982). Although we will not go into details about the morphological analysis, I would like to mention that the morpheme [l] has been associated with person (cf. Bonet 1991, 1995; Bernstein 2008) and also with definiteness (cf. Leonetti 1999; Leu 2005; Wiltschko 2002). In general, in the literature, it has been argued that the morpheme [l] of pronouns corresponds to the definite article (cf. Abney 1987; Postal 1969; Roca 1992, 1996; Uriagereka, among others), although authors like

(38) DATIVE = ACCUSATIVE + [i]

[Taken from Martin 2012]

The empirical arguments underlying the analysis are diverse. A piece of evidence comes from the Catalan colloquial form exemplified in (36) that reveals the underlying structure of dative clitics.

(39) [əlzi] dono el llibre.
CL.DAT.3PL give the book
'I give the book to them.'

Boeckx and Martin (2013) argue that the structure of the clitic [əlzi] is that given in (40). The morpheme [ə] corresponds to the accusative clitic, [z] to the plural feature and [i] to the locative clitic.

(40) AC[əlz] LOC[i]

Both authors show that the dative clitic features a set of peculiarities that account for its hybrid character. One of the first arguments that they mention is that the dative clitics do not present an homogeneous group. As it is known, from a semantic point of view, the dative can present different values (cf. Huidobro 2008). The dative clitic can have an argumental character (*i.e.* playing different thematic roles: goal, benefactor, possessor, and experimenter) and also be located in non-argumentative positions (*i.e.* with an ethical value)¹².

The behavior of the dative clitic when combined with other clitics also seems to reflect its compositional character. As seen in (43), the plural dative clitic supports the interpolation of a partitive clitic.

(41) De pomes, en donaré als nens demà
of apples CL.PART will.give to.the children tomorrow
'Apples, I will give it to the children tomorrow.'

(42) Als nens, [elzi] donaré pomes demà
to.the children, CL.DAT.3PL will.give apples tomorrow
'To the children, I will give apples tomorrow.'

(43) De pomes, als nens, [elzeni]
of apples to.the children, CL.DAT.3PL CL.PART
donaré demà.
will.give tomorrow

Roca (1992, 1996) defend that this correspondence is only valid in the case of the accusative clitic.

¹² In addition, heads that introduce the dative complement appear in different positions. With this we refer to the positions that can occupy the different types of applications that introduce the indirect complement (cf. Pytkkanen 2002, 2008; Jeong 2006, 2007; among others).

'Apples, to the children, I will give tomorrow.'

3.3.2. The structure of the clitic and cross-linguistic variation

This subsection shows in more detail how the internal structure of each clitic is organized. Here, I assume that the third-person dative and that the accusative clitics are introduced by a KP (Kase phrase) projection associated with structural case (cf. Bittner and Hale 1996; Kayne 2002, 1994; Siegel 1974, among others). A representation of both clitics is shown bellow (accusative cf. (44), dative cf. (45)).

As seen in (44), the accusative clitic is introduced by a KP layer that takes a DP as a complement. The same process occurs in the dative clitic, which, as mentioned earlier, presents a more complex structure than the accusative. In particular, (45) shows a KP and DP layer corresponding to the accusative clitic. As for the PP layer in (45), it corresponds to the locative clitic (following the analysis of the locatives in Kayne 1975).

An interesting question that arises about the structure of (45) is whether there is cross-linguistic variation with respect to the internal composition of the dative. This question is relevant if we consider that not all languages superficially present a locative clitic. Although Boeckx and Martin (2013) develop their proposal based on data from Catalan, it extends, at least, to the whole range of Romance languages. As the authors point out, the 'primitive' or 'derived' condition of a given element should be a universal feature. The question that arises is what happens in languages that do not possess a system of clitics as rich as the Catalan pronominal system, as occurs, for example, in Spanish.

Looking at this in more detail, the Catalan clitic paradigm has differentiated forms for the locative clitic *hi* and the dative clitic *li*. Present-day Spanish, however, has lost the locative clitic and manifests the following form for the dative clitic: *le*. As mentioned before, dative clitics in Spanish present, in the same way as in Catalan, a locative clitic in an underlying way. The crucial difference I wish to emphasize here is that the structure of (42) would not be productive in Spanish. That is to say: the combination of a locative clitic and an accusative clitic is not possible in this language. In other words, the locative

and the accusative clitic cannot be combined in the syntax to give rise to a dative clitic, which is something that could occur in Catalan.

In the case of Spanish, the structure of the dative clitic is created in the lexicon and constitutes an element that syntax manipulates as a unit. On the contrary, the dative structure of Catalan is formed in the syntax, where accusative and locative merge. The structure that corresponds to the Catalan dative can be observed in (43)¹³, where the layer corresponding to the locative clitic (PP) and the layer corresponding to the accusative (KP and DP) can be differentiated. In Spanish, however, both layers are not visible.

(46) a. [_{KP} K [_{PP} P [_{DP} D]]] (Catalan dative)
b. Clitic *li*, where *i* is locative (PP)

(47) a. [_{KP} K [_{DP} D + P]] (Spanish dative)
b. Clitic *le*, where do not Surface locative

The (im)possibility of merging both categories is what gives rise to a series of effects of cross-linguistic variation. These same effects can be found in this case, as will be discussed in the next section.

3.4. The combinatorial restriction

This section discusses the data on clitic combinations presented in Section 2 from the point of view of the Distinctness Condition (cf. Richards 2010). Furthermore, this section develops a proposal that points out the different alterations and incompatibilities that occur in the combinations within this model.

In the previous section, I argued that clitic clusters are transferred together, as they end up within the same domain: the edge of v^* . In addition, I showed that clitics are introduced by the same functional category: KP. Finally, I claimed that the fundamental difference between the dative clitic and the accusative clitic is that the former presents deixis (represented by the locative clitic *hi*). In this section, I show how the different combinatorial constraints follow from under these assumptions.

Before going ahead, let us repeat Richards' DIS (2010) for the ease of reference:

(48) Distinctness

If a linearization statement $\langle \alpha, \alpha \rangle$ is generated, the derivation crashes at PF.

[Taken from Richards, 2010: 5]

As developed in more detail in section 3.2.1., the Distinctness Condition is a restriction that arises due to the impossibility of linearizing two functional categories that have an identical label. This restriction applies to each structure fragment that is transferred to the phonetic interface (each Transfer Domain). Let us see how the combinatorial restriction operates in the combination of a dative clitic and an accusative clitic in third person (cf. Section 2).

¹³ As mentioned by Ordóñez and Roca (2014), the morphological structure of the clitics in question highlights this observation. In Spanish the dative clitic presents an epenthetic *e* in the sense of Harris (1992), in the Catalan dative clitic *li*, on the other hand, the *i* corresponds to the locative.

Going back to the structure presented in the previous section, both clitics have an identical label: <KP, KP>. In addition, as it is exemplified in (49) both labels are within the same domain: the edge of a phase.

(49)

The combination of both clitics is, therefore, a violation of the Distinctness Condition. Recall that Richards (2010) mentions three different strategies to solve the creation of a non-convergent derivation, such as (49): (i) elimination of structure, (ii) movement, and, finally, (iii) addition of structure with phase status.

As described in section 2, the variation observed concerning the combination of two third person clitics are wide. Here, I claim that most of the alterations correspond to the elimination of structure, one of the strategies mentioned by Richards (2010) to avoid the linearization of two identical labels (in this case <KP, KP>). As it can be seen below, this strategy is not possible in all cases and some varieties resort to the insertion of another clitic.

In the next section, I pay attention to the variation observed in the different alterations. Finally, in section 3.5.2., I explain the reasons why I consider that the strategy used is the elimination of structure and then I elaborate in more detail on this strategy.

3.5. The cross-linguistic variation

As described in section 4, the variation with respect to the different alterations manifested by the clitics is broad. In this section, I focus on the Catalan case first, and then I will move to the Spanish and Aragonese facts.

The examples in (50) show the different solutions that Catalan deploys.

- (50)
- | | | |
|----|------------|-----------|
| a. | lo | hi |
| | CL. | |
| | AC.3SG | CL.LOC |
| b. | li | |
| | CL.DAT.3SG | |
| c. | l' | hi |
| | CL.AC.3SG | CL.LOC |

What is relevant in the results of (50) is that they all correspond to the dative structure mentioned in subsection 3.3.1: accusativity and locativity. A closer look at (50) reveals that the combination of an accusative clitic and a dative clitic of third person constitutes the combination of the following structures:

- (51) [_{KP} K [_{PP} P [_{DP} D]]] (DATIVE)
 (52) [_{KP} K [_{DP} D]] (ACCUSATIVE)

As mentioned, this combination is not possible because a non-linearizable structure <KP, KP> is generated. The solution used in Catalan is to eliminate the accusative part of the dative clitic (KP), so that the final result is as shown in (53), *i.e.* the locative clitic.

- (53) [~~_{KP} K~~ [_{PP} P [~~_{DP} D~~]]] → [_{PP} P]

Thus, the structure to be linearized is <KP, PP> instead of *<KP, KP> (illegitimate under Richards' 2010 Distinctness). And the underlying structure of the combinations in (47) is in all cases as follows:

- (50) [_{KP} K [_{DP} D] [_{PP} P]]

Second, in Spanish, the results of the combination of third person accusative and dative clitics are the following:

- | | | | |
|------|----|-------------------------|-------------------------|
| (51) | a. | se
SE | lo
CL.LOC |
| | b. | se
SE | le
CL.DAT.3SG |
| | c. | le
CL.DAT.3SG | |

Except for the case of (51c), the elimination of structure does not seem possible in the previous cases. As I have argued in the previous section, the reason for this is that the internal structure of the dative clitic in Spanish differs from that of Catalan in a fundamental aspect. That aspect is that the locative clitic and the accusative are merged in the lexicon to form the dative clitic. And that is why it does not present a differentiated form for both clitics in the syntax.

As a consequence, it is not possible to eliminate the structure corresponding to the accusative part of the clitic dative, since it does not present a differentiated constituent of the locative. In varieties that allow null objects (Basque Spanish, Quiteño Spanish), the solution is not to realize this object. In contrast, varieties that do not allow null objects insert the clitic SE.

Regarding the appearance of this clitic, I will assume that it presents a totally different structure to the one of accusative and dative clitics. This clitic possesses a head (X⁰) status, unlike the XP status of the accusative and dative clitics (following Gallego and Uriagereka 2016). Specifically, what this means is that SE involves a structure similar to that of an expletive probe (similar to *there* in English, cf. Uriagereka 1988, Kayne 2000, Chomsky 2004). Thus, the structure that must be linearized is as follows:

(52) <X°, KP>

An issue that we can consider now, is how the dative interpretation is maintained in the case of (52). As Kayne (2000) points out, the clitic SE is similar to locative clitics in other Romance varieties. We can find examples where the clitics *le* and *se* can manifest locative interpretation:

- (53) a. Puse el mantel en la mesa .
 put the tablecloth in the table
 'I put the tablecloth in the table.'
 b. **Le** puse el mantel (a la mesa).
 CL.DAT.3SG put the tablecloth to the table
 'I put the tablecloth in the table.'

- (54) a. Puse el mantel en la mesa .
 put the tablecloth in the table
 'I put the tablecloth in the table.'
 b. **Se lo** puse.
 SE CL.AC.3SG put
 'I put the tablecloth in the table.'

(Gallego and Uriagereka 2016)

Therefore, the clitic SE plays a double role. On the one hand, it permits a linearizable structure: such as <X, KP>. On the other hand, it can maintain the semantic content of dative clitics by expressing locative meaning.

Finally, let me go back to the combinations of Aragonese (cf. (55)).

- (55) a. **l'** **en**
 CL.AC.3SG CL.PART
 b. **els** **ie**
 CL.AC.3PL CL.LOC

The combination in (55b) corresponds to the same combination that can be observed in Catalan: accusative and locative. This combination is precisely the one that appears in the Aragonese dialect that comes into contact with the Catalan area. Regarding the combination (55a), the strategy used is different. Western, Southern, and Central Aragonese varieties use a different strategy to avoid the linearization of two elements of the same type <KP, KP>. The accusative clitic is replaced by the partitive clitic, which constitutes a PP (following Kayne 2000). The linearization system, therefore, receives a linearizable structure: <KP, PP>.

The question that arises at this point is why Aragonese resorts to a strategy different from the one that Catalan uses if both languages present an apparently identical pronominal system. The answer, I argue, is that the Aragonese pronominal system has

some divergences from the Catalan system. As can be observed in (56) and (57), these clitics behave differently.

- (56) a. Sí, puede **bi** haber **-ne.** (Aragonese)
 yes can CL.LOC there.be CL.PART
 'Yes, there may be.'
- b. Sí, puede **bi** 'n haber. (Aragonese)
 yes can CL.LOC CL.PART there.be
 'Yes, there may be.'
- (57) a. *Sí, pot **hi** haver **-ne.** (Catalan)
 yes can CL.LOC there.be CL.PART
 'Yes, there may be.'
- b. *Sí, pot **n'** **hi** haver. (Catalan)
 yes can CL.PART CL.LOC there.be
 'Yes, there may be.'

The locative clitic in Western Aragonese variants may occupy an intermediate position between the modal verb and the infinitive. This feature has been related with the possibility that the locative clitic in Aragonese is losing its productivity. The locative clitic in Aragonese seems to be in an intermediate step between Catalan, language that maintains the productive locative clitic, and Spanish that has lost it. This would be the reason why Aragonese cannot resort to the elimination of structure, maintained in Catalan.

From this one can safely conclude that the alterations manifested by clitics in the combinations respond to a distinctive necessity. This necessity arises from the impossibility of linearizing two elements with identical label <KP, KP>. As will be developed below, the option of eliminating structure is preferable to the other strategies mentioned by Richards (2010): the insertion of structure and movement. In the next section, I focus on this strategy.

3.5.2. The 'repair strategies' in the system

The question that arises in relation to the examples analyzed in the previous section is how these alterations can occur in the system. Specifically, the question is whether the syntax can create a non-convergent clitic combination and repair it at some point in the derivation (what is known as a 'repair strategy'). In the minimalist program (cf. Chomsky 1995, 2000, 2001) this possibility has been rejected. The alteration of the created structure is an uneconomical operation and it also violates a series of general principles. As mentioned above, one of the principles that it violates is the Non-tampering Condition (cf. Chomsky 1995) and the Inclusiveness Condition (cf. Chomsky 2008). If we assume the existence of a 'repair strategy' that modifies the structure created, either by adding or eliding elements, these conditions are violated.

In this paper, I will not assume that the syntax can alter the structure already created so that the derivations are legitimate, since this would violate the mentioned principles.

The only operation that I consider legitimate is the elision of part of the structure. Specifically, the option of eliminating structure to which we have resorted in the previous section can be reinterpreted as a process in which the Phonetic Form does not phonetically make a certain constituent.

In this way, it is not necessary to postulate a 'repair strategy' that eliminates part of the structure already created. The idea I would like to outline here is that the preferred tendency for the system is to continue with the derivation created trying to 'readjust' the impossible combination in the phonetic interface. The only process allowed at this level is the non-phonetic realization of some constituent. This is precisely what happens in Catalan and in the Eastern Aragonese variety, where the ellipsis of one layer corresponds to the accusative part of the dative clitic. This is not a challenge for linearization since, as we have discussed above, elements that do not present phonetic realization are inserted for the effects of distinctivity.

Conversely, when the elision is not possible, the derivation fails and generates a new structure. This would happen in the combination of the clitics in Spanish and in the remaining Aragonese varieties. In this case, a new derivation is created and the elements to be linearized are totally different from the original ones.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has analysed the combinatorial constraints that occur in clitic combinations. To do this, I focused on the combination of third person clitics. In particular, I explore this restriction in different Eastern Iberian Romance languages (Catalan, Aragonese and Spanish) and I have described the variation attested.

Moreover, this paper has put forward a proposal according to the Distinctness Condition. Following this condition, clitic clusters are constrained due to the appearance of two identical labels <KP, KP> within the same Transfer Domain (edge of v^*).

In particular, I defend that third person accusative and dative clitics present a KP category and are generated in the edge of vP^* . The object to be linearized is, therefore, of type <KP, KP>. As discussed in section 3, this object cannot be linearized. The alterations on the linearization of an object <KP, KP> are diverse.

I have argued that the preferred alternative is to not perform phonetically a part of the structure (a syntactic constituent), so that the resulting object lacks one of the two identical labels. This happens in Catalan and in the Oriental Aragonese varieties, where the KP layer of the dative is elided, generating an object of type <KP, PP>.

(58) **L'** **hi** diré.
 CL.AC.3SG CL.LOC will.say
 'I will say it to him/her.'

(59) Els bous **els** **ie** compro a ell.
 the owen CL.AC.3PL CL.LOC buy to him
 I buy him the owen.'

In the varieties of Spanish that allow null objects, this elision permits the linearization of this object (cf. (60)).

(60) ¿Quién **le** contó? Dicen que **le** contó su hermana

who CL.DAT.3SG tell said that CL.DAT.3SG tell his sister
 Who told it to him/her? They said that his sister tell it to him/her.'

When the elision is not possible, the object <KP, KP> is rejected by the system and a new one is generated. In the case of Spanish, the new combination consists of a clitic that presents the category of a head (clitic SE) and that also maintains the dative interpretation, as I have previously mentioned.

- (61)
- | | | | | | |
|------|-----------|--|-----------|--|--------|
| Juan | se | | lo | | compró |
| Juan | SE | | CL.AC.3SG | | bought |
- 'Juan bought it to him/her.'

Finally, in the case of the Central, Western, and Southern Aragonese variants, the clitic that appears is the partitive, which creates an object of type <KP, PP>.

- (62)
- | | | | | | |
|--------|--------|--|------------|--|---------|
| Marta, | torna | | lis | | ne |
| Marta, | return | | CL.DAT.3PL | | CL.PART |
- 'Marta, return it to them immediately.'

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